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Effect of Measurement, Observation and Classification Skills on Students' Academic Achievement in Biology in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Having a full grasp of the science process skills is an important factor in the academic journey of science students, especially in biology. This study examines specially the effect of measurement, observation, and classification skills on students' academic achievement in biology in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design, with a pre-test-post-test, non-equivalent control group design. The study population comprised all three private secondary schools in Igbo-Imabana, in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. A simple random sampling technique of balloting was used to select two (2) schools for the study. The sample for the study consisted of 129 senior secondary school students. The 129 students were divided into two groups: 64 for the experimental test and 65 for the control group, using simple random sampling technique as well as balloting. One school was assigned the experimental group, while the other school was assigned the control group, respectively. The instructional (treatment) package on Human Skeletal System and Biology Performance Test (BPT) were the instruments used for the study. The instruments were subjected to face validity with 20-item questions submitted to two lecturers, one biology expert and one expert in test and measurement. Biology Performance Test was trialled on 30 students who were not part of the main study. The collected data were coded and analysed using Kuder Richardson Formula-21 to determine the internal consistency of the Biology Performance Test (BPT), which yielded a coefficient index of 0.87. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while analysis of co-variance

(ANCOVA) was used for testing the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The pre-test scores were used as covariates for the post-test scores. The ANCOVA was employed to partially explain the initial differences between both groups. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with the expository method. There is no interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) or gender on the academic achievement of students in biology. It was recommended, among others, that curriculum planners, who are in charge of all activities guiding teaching and learning in the classroom, should design curriculum contents such as the use of scientific skills for teaching delivery by teachers and acquisition by students.

Keywords: measurement, observation, classification, science process skills, and biology

1. Introduction

The global acknowledgment of science and technology as a significant catalyst for technological progress cannot be overemphasized. This is attributed to the essential role that knowledge and proficiency in scientific subjects play in the advancement of any community, as noted by Bena (2010). Science process skills act as a tool that motivates learners to engage in tasks, thereby fostering reflective thinking and the discovery of knowledge. This process contributes to the development of a scientific character, aligning with the objectives of modern science education, which emphasises the validation of conclusions through observation of natural phenomena.

The development of scientific skills in students provides essential components for the general goals of education. Scientific skills occur naturally and spontaneously in most of our individual minds as we engage in thoughts. However, the process of logically breaking down steps in our thinking about the world and how to answer our questions, either consciously or unconsciously, about how the world works involves the use of scientific skills (Malhi 2017).

Science skill acquisition is the foundation for the effective learning of science. Al-Rabaani (2014) defined science as a way of explaining events and phenomena in nature, and so it is a continuous search or attempt to finding a more accurate description of things and events. This search leads to new discoveries or knowledge and requires one

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to arrive at new discoveries. Science as a body of knowledge is acquired through systematic experimentation, which involves the processes of doing things using the sense organs. Through sense experience, we learn many things about nature by asking questions and finding answers to these questions. This enables us to interact effectively with nature.

The acquisition of appropriate scientific skills is necessary to cope with the academic challenges in learning science-related subjects like biology. Biology is one of the science subjects that deals with the study of life and structure of living things. The study of biology in senior secondary schools using scientific skills acquisition will enable students to have a good knowledge of concepts and principles that will help them explore their desired field of endeavour.

The Nigerian Educational Research Council (NERC) in 1990 came up with fifteen (15) science process skills, namely: observing, drawing, classifying, identifying, predicting, measuring, communicating, inferring, questioning, controlling, hypothesising, designing experiments, and interpreting data, amongst others.

Observation is an important science skill; it involves using all of the senses, as appropriate, to find out about the characteristics, properties, and attributes of objects, places, and events. Observation can be made directly with the senses or indirectly through the use of instruments that extend our capacity to observe. Classification skills are an investigative approach that involves sorting objects or events into groups or categories. Classification and identification are important because they allow us to better understand relationships and connections between things. They also help scientists communicate clearly with each other.

Measuring skills involve using both standard and non-standard measurements or estimates to describe the dimension of an object or event. The ability to identify the measurement required, specify the instrument to be used, compare the measurement with a specific instrument, and add up the total measurement for the purpose of determining accuracy is a demonstration of measurement skills.

Gender plays a major role in achievement, and it may be possible that gender disparities could affect the acquisition of science process skills and invariable achievement among students in junior secondary schools. On the other hand, there is the underlying belief that boys and girls differ in their intellectual abilities and that boys tend to be more interested in task-oriented subjects like the sciences than girls (Akolonu,

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2001). Viadero (1998) seems to be of the opinion that the nature of performance is the product of heredity and exposure to the environment and not of sex.

Scientific skills are special skills that simplify the learning of science activities, make students very committed to their learning or studies, and also develop students' sense of responsibility. It increases the permanence of learning and research methods. Scientific process skills are critical to the learner because they help students develop their creativity by making them think like scientists (Karamustafaoglu, 2011).

Nnoli (2015) carried out a related study on students' classroom observation skills and students' academic achievement in chemistry. Two research questions guided the study. The design of the study was a descriptive survey. The study was conducted in Anambra State, Nigeria, and the study population consisted of all the private and public secondary school teachers. The researcher concluded that observational skills through effective classroom management create a safe classroom environment for chemistry students.

Daramola and Olutola (2016) examined the effects of some selected science process skills on students' academic performance in practical biology in Ilorin, Nigeria, and came up with the suggestion that students should be given the opportunity to explore the world of biology by using the science process skills of manipulating, drawing, classifying, inferring, interpreting, measuring, observing, and possibly problem-solving, as they have a significant contribution to students' academic lives.

Eric (2013) examined the effects of selected science process skills on students' academic performance in biology practical in Bungoma West District, Western Kenya. A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. Findings of the study showed that strategies adopted in helping students acquire the science process skills of drawing, measuring, identifying, classifying, and inferring of biological specimens were inadequate. Eric further stressed that the problems encountered in making drawings, measuring, and inferring by students and the strategies used by teachers to develop those skills in students have a significant effect on their academic performance in practical biology.

Sani (2015) examined the difference of science process approach on remedial science students' achievement in Jigawa State, Nigeria. The major objective of the study was to determine whether or not exposure to science process skills (including measuring skills) has any significance on the achievement in biology among students in Jigawa

State. Major findings of the study revealed that the process approach does not seem to be more effective than the lecture method in enhancing academic performance in science.

A study carried out by Nwosu (2020) on "Level of Acquisition of Science Process Skills among SS1 Senior Secondary School Students" found that no significant interactive effect of teaching method and gender was found on the mean achievement scores of students in methods of teaching. Also, a study carried out by Okeke (2018) on women's and girls' participation in science, technology, and mathematics discovered a significant interactive effect of gender and treatment on achievement.

Rauf (2013) conducted a study that investigated a new teaching strategy called differentiated strategy and tested its effect on the science process skills development. His study was formed with the aim of helping teachers devise a strategy that will suit the continuously growing diversity among learners at present. The skills that he tested in his study are measuring, comparing, classifying, and problem solving. It has proven the null hypothesis, which states that there was a significant difference between the mean gain score of the pupils in the experimental and control groups in terms of skills in comparing, measuring, and problem solving. Thus, it can be said that science is still a subject that requires several strategies to cope with the vastly changing learning environment of students.

The importance of biology cannot be undermined. However, to enhance the academic performance of students in biology, there is need for learners to acquire scientific skills that will help them understand difficult concepts in biology. However, such scientific skills include measurement, observation, and classification skills. These skills are appropriate for all science fields, and they reflect on the correct behaviour of scientists while they are solving a problem and planning an experiment. They also constitute thinking and research within science (Raj & Davis, 2014; Yumusak, 2016).

Statement of the Problem

The objectives of biology cannot be attained without its *practicals*. Despite the relevance of biology to technological, scientific, and societal development, evidence abounds that students' performance in biology is still not encouraging.

Scientific skills among the secondary school students seemed to be poorly developed considering the fact that not many students are exposed to science practical activities at the aforementioned levels. There is urgent need to encourage science

students to participate actively in science-related activities that would boost the development of scientific skills. Research studies reveal that students' non-acquisition of scientific skills could be as a result of the method of teaching biology concepts, non-coverage of syllabus, school factors, societal factors, as well as students and teachers' attitudes towards science practical activities, among others.

However, for learners to acquire basic scientific skills, there is need to further explore other possible innovative approaches that may help curb students' poor performance in biology. Will designing an instructional package on the human skeletal system improve students' acquisition of scientific skills? Will the acquisition of scientific skills have an interactive effect on students' academic performance in biology in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

This study was carried out to determine the effect of science process skills like measuring, classification, etc. on students' academic achievement in biology in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It has the following specific objectives:

1. Determine the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with the expository method.
2. Determine the interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on the academic achievement of students in biology.

Research Questions

The following research questions were stated to guide the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with the expository method?
2. What is the interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on the academic achievement of students in biology?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were postulated and used for the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with expository method.

H₀₂: There is no interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on academic achievement of students in biology.

2. Method

This study adopted the quasi-experimental research design. Specifically, it is a pretest – post-test non-equivalent control group design. The study population comprised of all three private secondary schools in Igbo-Imabana, in Abi Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. The purposive sampling was used based on the following criteria: Such school must have a well installed Science Laboratory Lab, has been established up to five years, as well as admits a considerable number of students every year. With these criteria, only two schools were qualified, namely Optimistic Secondary School, Igbo-Imabana and Assurance Secondary School, Igbo-Imabana. A simple random sampling technique of balloting was used to select two (2) schools for the study. In this method, a list of three private secondary schools was folded and put into a container, a student was blindfolded to choose from the container, among the three schools that were folded. Two schools were then selected for the study bearing the schools under investigation. The sample for the study consisted of 129 senior secondary two students. The 129 students were divided into two groups of 64 for experiment and 65 for control group using simple random sampling technique as well as balloting. One school was assigned the experimental group while the other school was assigned control group, respectively. Instructional (treatment) package on the Human Skeletal System and Biology Performance Test (BPT) were the instruments used for the study. The instruments were face-validated with a 20 item questions submitted to two lecturers, one biology expert and one expert in test and measurement. Biology Performance Test was trial-tested on 30 students who were not part of the main study. The data collected were coded and analyzed using the Kuder Richardson Formula-21 to determine the internal consistency for Biology Performance Test (BPT) which yielded a coefficient index of 0.87. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used in answering the

research questions while analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was used for testing the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The pre-test scores were used as covariates to the post-test scores. The ANCOVA was employed to partial out the initial differences between the both groups.

3. Results

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using Science Process Skills Acquisition and those taught with Expository method?

Table 4.1: Mean, Standard Deviation and Mean difference scores of students taught biology using Science Process Skills Acquisition and those taught with Expository method

Treatment Group	n	Pretest \bar{x}	SD	Posttest \bar{x}	SD	Mean Difference
Science Process Skills Acquisition (Experimental)	64	11.68	3.02	28.75	6.26	17.07
Expository method (Control)	65	12.00	3.39	13.78	4.51	1.78

The result in table 4.1 shows the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with expository method. The result shows that the pre-test score of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition was 11.68 with a standard deviation of 3.02 and a post-test mean of 28.75, with a standard deviation of 6.26, and mean difference of 17.07. Whereas, the pre-test of students taught biology using expository method was 12.00, with a standard deviation of 3.39 and a post-test mean of 13.78, with a standard deviation of 4.51. The mean difference for students taught biology using expository method was 1.78. The result indicates that the mean difference of scientific skills acquisition of experimental group is higher than that of the expository method (control group). The result implies that science process skills acquisition seems more effective in increasing academic achievement of students in biology.

Research Question Two

What is the interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on academic achievement of students taught biology?

Table 4.2: Mean, Standard Deviation and Mean difference in the interactive Effect of Treatment (methods of teaching) and Gender on Academic Achievement of Students taught Biology

Treatment	Gender	N	Pretest \bar{X}	SD	Posttest \bar{X}	SD	Mean Difference
Science Process Skills Acquisition	Male	23	11.73	3.15	28.52	6.21	16.79
	Female	41	11.65	2.99	28.87	6.37	17.22
Expository method	Male	25	12.48	3.38	12.06	3.46	-0.42
	Female	40	11.70	3.40	14.30	3.46	2.60
							5.03

The data in table 4.2 show the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using science process skills acquisition. The result shows that male students had a pre-test mean of 11.73 with a standard deviation of 3.15, and a post-test mean of 28.52 with a standard deviation of 6.21. The difference between the pre-test and post-test means for male students was 16.79, whereas, female students had a pre-test mean of 11.65 with a standard deviation of 2.99 and a post-test mean of 28.87 with a standard deviation of 6.37. The difference between the pre-test and post-test means for female students was 17.22. For both male and female taught using science process skills acquisition, the post-test means were greater than the pre-test means with female having a slightly higher mean increase than the male students.

In order hand table 4.2 further reveals the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught biology using expository method. The result showed that male students had a pretest mean of 12.48 with a standard deviation of 3.38 and a posttest mean of 12.06 with a standard deviation of 3.46. The difference between the pretest and posttest means for male students was -0.42. Whereas, female students had a pretest mean of 11.70 with a standard deviation of 3.40 and a post-test mean of

14.30 with a standard deviation of 5.03. The difference between the pre-test and post-test means for female students was 2.60.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with expository method.

Table 4.3: Result of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the significant Difference in the Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Biology using Science Process Skills Acquisition and those taught with Expository method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	7382.730 ^a	2	3691.365	128.462	.000
Intercept	2561.972	1	2561.972	89.158	.000
Pretest	160.366	1	160.366	5.581	.020
Methods of Teaching	7310.607	1	7310.607	254.414	.000
Error	3620.618	126	28.735		
Total	69032.000	129			
Corrected Total	11003.349	128			

a. R Squared = .671 (Adjusted R Squared = .666)

The result in table 4. 3 shows that an F-ratio of 254.414 with an associated probability value of 0.000 was obtained with regards to the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with expository method. Since the associated probability of 0.000 was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis one which states that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with expository method was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with expository method.

Hypothesis Two

There is no interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on academic achievement of students in biology.

Table 4.4: Result of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the interactive Effect of Treatment (Methods of Teaching) and Gender on Academic Achievement of students in Biology

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	7425.212 ^a	4	1856.303	64.330	.000
Intercept	2425.210	1	2425.210	84.045	.000
Pretest	173.353	1	173.353	6.008	.016
Methods of Teaching	6942.375	1	6942.375	240.587	.000
Gender	30.279	1	30.279	1.049	.308
Methods of Teaching * Gender	11.515	1	11.515	.399	.529
Error	3578.136	124	28.856		
Total	69032.000	129			
Corrected Total	11003.349	128			

a. R Squared = .675 (Adjusted R Squared = .664)

Data presented in table 4.4 shows that an F-ratio of 0.399 with an associated probability value of 0.529 was obtained with regards to interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on academic achievement of students in biology. Since the associated probability of 0.243 was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis three which states that there is no interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on academic achievement of students in biology was retained. This implies that there is no interactive effect on treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on academic achievement of students in biology.

4. Discussion

Teaching Methods and Students' Academic Achievement

The summary of the analysis for research question and hypothesis one reveals that science process skills acquisition seems more effective in increasing the academic

achievement of students in biology than the expository method. Similarly, there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught biology using science process skills acquisition and those taught with the expository method. This finding is in accordance with the work of Nnoli (2015), who found that the acquisition of observational skills in chemistry classroom makes students to participate actively and maximise learning, which allows students interaction for academic achievement. This finding is also in agreement with Aruna and Sunn (2010), who found that the measuring approach was superior to the constructivist model of teaching for increasing attitudes towards science and performance in biology. **On the contrary**, the finding of this study disagrees with Sani (2015), who found that process approach does not seem to be more effective than the lecture method in enhancing academic performance in science.

Interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) and gender on academic achievement

Analysis for research question and hypothesis two reveals that there is no interactive effect of treatment (methods of teaching) or gender on academic achievement of students in biology. This finding agrees with Nwosu (2020), who found that no significant interactive effect of teaching method and gender was found on the mean achievement scores of students in methods of teaching. Conversely, the findings of this study are not in line with Okeke (2018), who in a study discovered a significant interactive effect of gender and treatment on achievement. Viadero (1998) seems to be of the opinion that the nature of performance is the product of heredity and exposure to the environment and not of sex.

5. Conclusion / Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Effective use of diverse instructional strategies should be utilised by teachers to enhance students' performance in biology.
2. Curriculum planners, who are in charge of all activities guiding teaching and learning in the classroom, should design curriculum contents such as the use of scientific skills for teaching delivery by teachers and acquisition by students.
3. School administrators should provide a rich learning environment for students to help reduce failure and improve academic achievement in biology.

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References

- Al-Rabaani, A. (2014). The acquisition of science process skill by Omanis pre-service social studies teachers. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 6(1), 13 – 19.
- Akalonu, G. C. (2001). Effect of female gender- curriculum materials on student's achievement and interest in integrated Science Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Karamustafaoglu, S. (2011). Improving the science process skills ability of science teachers using diagrams. *European Journal of Physics and Chemistry Education*, 3(1), 26 – 38.
- Malhi, R. K. (2017). Skill development is key to economic progress role of higher education in India. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 4(3), 174 – 177.
- Raj, R. G. & Devi, S. N. (2014). Science process skills and achievement in science among high school students. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(15), 2435 – 2443.
- Viadeo, A., (1998). Gender equity awareness and interaction in the class-room. <http://www.org/TE/edu/gendiff>. Retrieved March 11, 2008.
- Daramola, D. S. & Olutola, A. T. (2016). Comparative effects of practical and alternative on practical methods on students' academic performance in Biology. *International Journal of Educational Benchmark* 3, 67 – 80.
- Okeke, E. A. C. (2018). Women and girls participation in science, technology and mathematics: educators as facilitators. In: G. A. Badmus and L. O. Ocho (eds.). *Science Mathematics and Technology Education in Nigeria*. Everlead Press, Lagos.

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Nwosu, A. A. (2020). Level of acquisition of science process skills among SS1 senior secondary school students. *Journal of the Science Teacher Association of Nigeria*, 29 (1&2), 47 – 53.

Nnoli, J. N. (2015). Interactive based, demonstration and learners centered: An evaluative approach in teaching Oxo-carbon. *Chemistry Panel Workshop Series*, 15, 28 – 31.